

Exploring the Nexus of Positive Childhood Experiences and Conflict Resolution Styles: Unveiling the Keys to Harmonious Relationship Dynamics

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Abstract

This research examines the association between positive childhood experiences of adults and their conflict resolution styles in romantic relationships, focusing on positive conflict resolution style, negative conflict resolution style, retreat conflict resolution style, and subordination conflict resolution style. The study investigates potential gender differences in positive childhood experiences and conflict resolution styles. A sample of 526 individuals, comprising 361 adult women and 165 adult men, in established romantic relationships was recruited through accessible sampling. Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS 26.0 package program and JASP. After confirming the normal distribution of the data, Pearson correlation analysis and independent t-test analysis techniques were utilized. Significance levels of .01 and .05 were considered for statistical evaluation. Results indicate a significant and positive relationship between positive childhood experiences and positive conflict resolution style, as well as a significant negative correlation between positive childhood experiences and negative conflict resolution style. Moreover, a positive and significant relationship was observed between positive childhood experiences and subordination conflict resolution style. However, no statistically significant relationship was found between positive childhood experiences and retreat conflict resolution style. Regarding gender differences in conflict resolution styles, only the subordination conflict resolution style showed a significant difference in favor of male participants. The study concludes by interpreting the findings in line with existing literature and providing recommendations.

Keywords: Positive childhood experiences, positive conflict resolution style, negative conflict resolution style, subordination, retreat

INTRODUCTION

Romantic relationships hold a significant place in individuals' lives. Romantic relationships are generally defined as partnership relationships between individuals who are dating, cohabiting, engaged, or married (Domingue & Mollen, 2009). Guided by the dynamics within the family system, romantic relationships are formed as interpersonal connections that establish the core of the family. Various studies have demonstrated the negative impact of loneliness and social isolation on physical health and lifespan (Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009; Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010; Uchino et al., 1996). On the other hand, research data suggests undeniable positive effects of romantic relationships on both men's and women's physical and mental health (Robles & Kiecolt-Glaser, 2003; Seligman, 2012). Considering these findings, it is important to explore various aspects of romantic relationships and the dynamics that influence them, with a focus on understanding healthy couple behaviors.

It is observed that researchers generally focus on childhood experiences that lead to personality disorders. In the past, there has been a dearth of attention dedicated to exploring the concepts of psychological resilience, positive experiences, and their consequential effects. However, in recent years, a notable shift in the research landscape has emerged, characterized by an escalating curiosity surrounding these topics (DeLuca et al., 2022; Gooding & Harris, 2020; Proyer et al., 2013; Waters, 2015; Yeager et al., 2017). Notably, positive experiences, protective factors, and psychological resilience have been identified as pivotal factors in ameliorating adverse life circumstances (Seligman, 2002). This growing recognition highlights the significance of understanding and promoting these factors to enhance individuals' well-being. Researchers argue that positive factors

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are more than just the opposite pole of negative risk factors (Fredrickson, 2003; Davidson et al., 2000). By examining the relationship between the presence or absence of positive experiences, it is suggested that positive experiences in individuals' lives can improve and protect them from challenging life conditions. Understanding the underlying processes of the relationship between positive experiences and challenging life conditions can provide suggestions on how adaptable thoughts and behaviors can be encouraged within therapeutic approaches.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000) introduced a new paradigm called positive psychology. This paradigm focuses on the science of positive experiences and behaviors (Lee Duckworth et al., 2005). Positive psychology proposes a new perspective to the dominant disease-based psychology understanding. The positive psychology paradigm suggests that researchers overlook perspectives they can learn from the healthy majority by focusing on clinical problems and behavioral disorders. Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000) emphasize the need for research efforts to focus on protective factors that are found in positive experiences and provide preventive approaches in psychopathology treatments.

Couples in romantic relationships can experience conflicts in every phase (Kurdek, 1994). Conflict resolution styles, within the context of romantic relationships, refer to the interpersonal behavioral patterns used to resolve disagreements (Marchand, 2004). Resolving conflicts is an integral part of a successful relationship, and it is likely that the attribution caused by partners and violations of personal space can fuel couples' arguments and hinder successful conflict resolution (Fincham et al., 2004). The ways in which couples resolve their conflicts are factors that influence the quality and duration of their intense relationship with their partners.

Observations by Gottman (1993) indicate that couples who discuss and resolve their relationship problems tend to do so in four ways: validating, invalidating, avoiding, and hostile. Each conflict resolution style has its own benefits and risks for partners. Relationships with a validating conflict style are characterized as calm, intimate, value-driven, and characterized by shared experiences. The potential risk in these relationships is the potential loss of romance, transitioning the relationship into a close friendship (Gottman & Levenson, 1992). Relationships with an invalidating approach, where conflicts are ignored, may make partners more resilient to the pain of arguments and confrontations, but the risky situation involves loneliness and emotional disconnection (Gottman, 1999; Hollman & Jarvis, 2003). Relationships with an avoiding style are centered around romance and passion. However, the risk in this situation is the perpetuation of unresolved conflicts. The hostile conflict style is marked by arguments and confrontations and encompasses many negative interaction patterns (Gottman, 1993). The impact of negative childhood experiences and childhood traumas on individuals' later lives is still being investigated. However, this knowledge will not provide insights into the effects of positive childhood experiences. It is believed that examining the influence of positive childhood experiences,

especially in romantic relationships that hold significant positions in individuals' lives and in the conflict resolution styles that affect the continuity of these relationships, will contribute significantly to the literature. The findings obtained from this research are expected to promote mutual understanding among couples to sustain their relationships, offer a new perspective to family and couple therapists in their approach to clients, draw attention to elements crucial for the holistic development of children in families, and provide new insights for researchers in the field.

Building upon the provided information, the current study aims to examine the relationship between positive childhood experiences and the utilization of conflict resolution styles within romantic relationships. Furthermore, the study seeks to explore whether there exists a noteworthy disparity in the conflict resolution styles employed by individuals in romantic relationships based on their gender. By investigating these factors, this study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how positive childhood experiences and gender may influence conflict resolution dynamics in romantic relationships.

METHOD

Participant and procedure

The sample for current study consists of 526 Turkish individual who have a romantic relationship (361 [68.6%] females and 165 [31.4%] males) which is aged 18-56 (Mage = 26.52, SD = 9.43). Participants were recruited by online questionnaire via web based platforms and partaked voluntarily. Participants asked for answer the measures evaluating (positive childhood experiences, conflict resolution styles scale in romantic relationships) and demographic information as well (eg., gender, age and romantic relationship status). The research project was approved by Ondokuz Mayıs University Social Sciences Research Ethics Boards (Report Number: 2020/605). We showed sample's characteristics in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample's characteristics

		N	%
Gender	Female	361	68,6
	Male	165	31,4
Relationship Status	Lover/Flirt	229	43,6
	Engaged / Committed	32	6,1
	Married	264	50,2
Duration of Relationship	Less than 6 months	89	16,9
	6 months - 12 months	50	9,5
	More than 1 year	387	73,6

Measures

Conflict Resolution Styles Scale in Romantic Relationships

Participants' Conflict Resolution Styles Scale in Romantic Relationships were assessed by using the scale developed by Ozen et al., (2016). Participants asked for assess 25 items (e.g, "When we encounter a problem, I distance myself from my

Table 2: Descriptive statistics, reliabilities and correlations for the study variables

Variable	Descriptive Statistics and Reliabilities							Correlations			
	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	α	ω	λ_6	1	2	3	4
1. Positive childhood experiences	80.17	18.79	-.577	-.281	.967	.969	.973	–			
2. Positive conflict resolution style	25.30	4.66	-.114	.204	.819	.794	.785	.28**	–		
3. Negative conflict resolution style	16.49	6.50	1.01	1.26	.797	.749	.770	-.19**	-.20**	–	
4. Subordination conflict resolution style	20.33	5.85	-.154	.712	.785	.787	.775	.11*	.13*	-.26**	–
5. Retreat conflict resolution style	21.83	6.17	.061	-.158	.765	.767	.772	.06	-.03**	-.08	.41**

partner.”) on a scale of 1 (none or very little) to 6 (most). There is 4 dimensions in the scale which is positive conflict resolution, negative conflict resolution, subordination conflict resolution, retreat conflict resolution styles. High scores obtained in each dimension indicate a tendency to use that conflict resolution style. It has been shown to have good internal consistency reliability in all dimensions of conflict resolution styles in romantic relationship scale ($\alpha_1 = .77$, $\alpha_2 = .80$, $\alpha_3 = .81$, $\alpha_4 = .75$).

Positive Childhood Experiences Scale

The Positive Childhood Experiences Scale was developed by Doğan and Aydın (2020) to assess participants' positive childhood experiences. Participants asked for assess 22 items (e.g., “My childhood memories are mostly positive. “) on a scale of 1 (disagree entirely) to 5 (absolutely agree). There is only dimensions in positive childhood experiences scale and high scores indicates more positive childhood experiences. It has been shown to perfect internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = .96$ and KMO = .97).

Data Analysis

Before analyzing the data of the study, skewness and kurtosis values were examined to determine whether the data showed a normal distribution. The examined skewness and kurtosis values of the scales of positive childhood experiences (-.577 and -.281), positive conflict resolution style (-.114 and .204), retreat conflict resolution style (.061 and -.158), acquiescence conflict resolution style (.120 and -.154), and negative conflict resolution style (1.018 and 1.260) indicated that the scores obtained from these scales exhibited a normal distribution (George & Mallery, 2010). Accordingly, Pearson correlation

analysis and independent samples t-test were employed to find answers to the research questions.

Results

This section includes information about the statistical analyses conducted to answer the research questions and presents the findings obtained from these analyses. The initial investigation focused on examining whether there is a significant association between the utilization of positive conflict resolution styles in adult romantic relationships and the presence of positive childhood experiences. The results of the descriptive statistics, reliabilities and Pearson correlation analysis for the study variables to determine the relationship between positive childhood experiences and conflict resolution styles in adult individuals are presented in Table 2.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis indicate a significant positive and low correlation between positive childhood experiences and positive conflict resolution style ($r = .283$, $p < .001$), a significant negative and weak relationship between positive childhood experiences and negative conflict resolution style ($r = -.189$, $p < .001$), a significant and low positive correlation between positive childhood experiences and the subordination conflict resolution style ($r = .106$, $p < .05$) and there was no significant relationship between positive childhood experiences and the retreat conflict resolution style ($r = .063$, $p > .05$).

The t-test analysis was conducted to examine whether there were statistically significant differences in positive, negative, retreat, and submission conflict resolution styles used by adult individuals in romantic relationships based on gender. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: T-test analysis examining the differentiation of conflict resolution styles in romantic relationships by gender

	Gender	N	Mean	sd	df	t	p
Positive conflict resolution	Female	361	25.68	4.65	524	1.23	.218
	Male	165	25.12	5.23			
Negative conflict resolution	Female	361	16.46	6.24		.41	.680
	Male	165	16.71	6.60			
Subordination conflict resolution	Female	361	19.79	5.89		4.55	.001
	Male	165	22.27	5.67			
Retreat conflict resolution	Female	361	21.92	6.19		1.90	.058
	Male	165	20.84	5.73			

The results from Table 3 indicate a significant gender difference in the utilization of the subordination conflict resolution style within romantic relationships ($t = 4.55, p < .01$). Specifically, it was found that male individuals exhibited a significantly higher tendency to employ the subordination style compared to their female counterparts in the context of romantic relationships. In contrast, no statistically significant differences were observed based on gender in the utilization of positive conflict resolution, negative conflict resolution, and retreat conflict resolution styles. These findings contribute to our understanding of how gender influences the selection of specific conflict resolution strategies within romantic relationships.

Discussion

In the present investigation, we aimed to build upon the existing literature by exploring the association between positive childhood experiences and individuals' conflict resolution style in romantic relationships. Literature shown that individuals who reported higher levels of happiness also demonstrated significantly enhanced skills in coping with stress (Kaya & Demir, 2017). Furthermore, empirical investigations yielded supportive evidence suggesting that individuals with well-developed stress coping abilities tended to adopt more constructive conflict resolution styles within their romantic relationships (Laursen, 1993; Doğan & Aydın, 2020). Drawing on the work of Noller (1995), our research underscores the influence of primary family unit interactions on individuals' engagement in interpersonal relationships. We found that the patterns of interaction established within the family unit played a crucial role in shaping individuals' conflict resolution styles within romantic relationships.

In our research, we not only explored the positive link between positive childhood experiences and constructive conflict resolution styles but also uncovered a negative association between positive childhood experiences and negative conflict resolution styles. These findings contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the impact of childhood experiences on individuals' conflict resolution dynamics within romantic relationships. Previous studies have highlighted the detrimental effects of negative childhood experiences, such as exposure to parental violence and living in violent communities, on the occurrence of dating violence among young adolescents (Finkelhor et al., 2007). Consistent with these findings, our research indicated that individuals who have been less positive childhood experiences are more prone to engaging in destructive conflict resolution strategies within their romantic relationships.

Furthermore, our study revealed that the absence of protective factors, including social support, close peer relationships, and a sense of belonging in school, increases the likelihood of adolescents engaging in dating violence and employing destructive conflict resolution approaches (Davis et al., 2019). These negative childhood experiences have been extensively associated with physical aggression, physical abuse, and revictimization through aggression in previous research.

Consequently, individuals who have undergone such adverse experiences tend to exhibit a propensity for violence towards their partners and engage in destructive approaches in their romantic relationships (Nikulina et al., 2021).

By highlighting the negative impact of less positive childhood experiences on conflict resolution styles, our research underscores the need for interventions and support systems to mitigate the long-term effects of adverse childhood experiences. Understanding the complex interplay between childhood experiences and conflict resolution dynamics is crucial for the development of targeted prevention and intervention strategies aimed at promoting healthy and constructive romantic relationships.

Additionally, in previous researches, negative parental attitudes, antisocial behaviors, and negative peer relationships during adolescence have been found to contribute to coercive behaviors in romantic relationships (Ha et al., 2012). Moreover, destructive parenting attitudes during early adolescence have been shown to predict partner coercion 15 years later. These findings suggest that healthy experiences with parents and peers during early stages hold promise for developing healthy adult intimate relationships (Ha et al., 2019).

The conducted study, we made several other noteworthy findings that contribute to the understanding of conflict resolution dynamics in romantic relationships. We found that individuals with avoidant attachment styles tend to exhibit a greater inclination towards retreat tendencies during conflicts. This aligns with previous studies that have demonstrated a significant association between retreat behavior and avoidant attachment style, indicating that individuals with an avoidant attachment style are more likely to engage in partner violence (Shi, 2003; Bonache et al., 2017)

Moreover, our research revealed a significant difference in the use of the accommodation conflict resolution style in romantic relationships based on gender. Specifically, we found that men tend to utilize the accommodation style more frequently than women. However, no significant gender differences were observed in the positive problem-solving, negative problem-solving, and retreat conflict resolution styles. This gender difference in the accommodation style can be attributed to the conflict resolution style employed by the partner. When the partner adopts constructive conflict resolution strategies, individuals may exhibit accommodation behavior to achieve effective resolution. Conversely, when the partner adopts a destructive conflict resolution approach, individuals may resort to accommodation as a means of avoiding conflict (Rusbult & Buunk, 1993).

These findings provide valuable insights into the complexities of conflict resolution in romantic relationships, shedding light on the interplay between attachment styles, gender, and conflict resolution strategies. To further enhance our understanding, future studies could delve deeper into these variations and explore additional factors that may influence conflict resolution dynamics in romantic relationships. By doing so, we can develop more comprehensive models and interventions aimed

at promoting healthier and more constructive conflict resolution strategies within couples.

Limitations and Future Directions

There are several limitations to consider when interpreting the results of this study. First, the use of cross-sectional data limits the ability to establish causality between the variables studied. The limitation of this study lies in its focus on descriptive relationships. Due to the dynamic nature of relationships, there is a need for further investigation beyond situational aspects. Second, the study relied on self-report measures from the participants. The use of experimental designs in laboratory settings could provide more objective assessments of individuals. As observed in the study, positive childhood experiences only account for a small portion of the nature of romantic relationships and conflicts. Further exploration is needed to gain a deeper understanding of romantic relationships and conflicts.

Overall, it is important to interpret the results of this study within the context of these limitations and consider the implications for future research.

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Consent to Participate: Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

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